

NATURAL FREQUENCIES OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED PLATES BASED ON REFINED HIGHER-ORDER SHEAR DEFORMATION THEORY

SID AHMED REFFAS

Laboratoire Mécanique et Physique Des Matériaux, Département Génie Mécanique, Faculté de Technologie, Université de Sidi Bel Abbès, BP 89 Cité Ben M'hidi, Sidi Bel Abbès, Algeria.

Email: reffas-ahmed@yahoo.fr

BENOUMRANE SALLAI

Département de Génie Civil et Des Travaux Publics, Faculté de Technologie, Université de Sidi Bel Abbès, BP 89 Cité Ben M'hidi, Sidi Bel Abbès, Algeria. Email: sallaiben@yahoo.fr

YASSINE KHALFI

Laboratoire de Génie des Procédés, Matériaux et Environnement, Département D'enseignements de Base en Sciences et de la Technologie, Faculté de Technologie, Université de Sidi Bel Abbès, BP 89 Cité Ben M'hidi, Sidi Bel Abbès, Algeria. Email: khalfi26yassine@yahoo.fr

BACHIR BOUIADJRA BACHIR*

LMPM, Institute of Maintenance and Industrial Safety, University of Oran 2 Mohamed Ben Ahmed, P.B 05 El M'naouer Oran Algeria. *Corresponding Author Email: bachir2imsi@gmail.com

Abstract

This study introduces an efficient shear strain theory for analyzing the vibration of functionally graded plates. The theory incorporates the parabolic distribution of transverse shear strains using a new hyperbolic warping function and meets zero-tension boundary conditions on the plate surfaces without employing shear correction factors. The mechanical properties of functionally graded plates are assumed to vary following a power-law distribution of the constituent volume fractions. The equations of motion are derived using the principle of variational energy and virtual work. Analytical solutions for the natural frequency are obtained for simply supported plates. The accuracy of these solutions is validated by comparing the results with those predicted by classical theory, first-order shear deformation theory, and higher-order shear deformation theory. It can be concluded that the proposed theory is both accurate and straightforward for predicting the natural frequencies of functionally graded plates.

Keywords: Vibration; Functionally Graded Material; New Hyperbolic Warping Function; Volume Fraction; Power Law Index; Natural Frequency.

1. INTRODUCTION

In traditional laminated composite structures, uniform elastic layers are bonded to enhance mechanical and thermal properties. However, a major drawback of this approach is the generation of significant interlaminar stresses at the interfaces, which can lead to delamination, matrix cracking, and other forms of damage. This is caused by the abrupt change in material properties across the layer interfaces. A solution to this issue is the use of Functionally Graded Materials (FGM), where material properties change continuously.

This is typically achieved by gradually varying the volume fraction of the constituent materials, usually in the thickness direction, to ensure a smooth transition in material properties. By leveraging the numerous possibilities offered by the FGM concept, it is expected that material performance will be enhanced and new functionalities developed. The concept of FGMs was introduced in 1984 by materials scientists in Japan [1].

Research on the vibration of functionally graded (FG) plates has garnered significant interest, leading to the development of various plate theories, including classical plate theory (CPT), first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT), and higher-order shear deformation theory (HSDT). The CPT ignores the effect of transverse shear deformation, providing accurate results only for thin plates, as demonstrated by [2-7], among others. For moderately thick plates, CPT tends to underestimate deflections while overestimating frequencies and buckling loads. The FSDT was developed to address the limitations of CPT by considering the transverse shear deformation effect through a linear variation of in-plane displacement across the thickness.

However, this approach disrupts equilibrium conditions at the top and bottom surfaces, necessitating the use of shear correction factors to adjust the unrealistic distribution of transverse shear stresses and strains. These correction factors depend on various parameters, including applied loads, boundary conditions, and geometric properties. Although FSDT provides acceptable results for moderately thick plates [8-12], determining the correct shear correction factor can be challenging, making it less convenient to use. To eliminate the need for shear correction factors, several HSDTs have been proposed, including those by [13-20], each varying in the number of unknowns they incorporate. Among these, Reddy's theory is the most commonly used due to its efficiency and simplicity [21-30]. Despite the cubic expansion of in-plane displacements in Reddy's theory complicating the equations of motion compared to FSDT, there remains a need to develop an accurate yet straightforward theory.

The aim of this study is to develop a shear deformation plate theory for functionally graded (FG) plates that is straightforward to use. This theory assumes that the in-plane and transverse displacements consist of bending and shear components, where the bending components do not contribute to shear forces and the shear components do not contribute to bending moments. A notable feature of this theory is its ability to account for a quadratic variation of transverse shear strains across the thickness while satisfying zero-traction boundary conditions on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate without the need for shear correction factors.

Additionally, it involves four unknowns and shares several similarities with the classical plate theory (CPT) in aspects such as equations of motion, boundary conditions, and stress resultant expressions. The material properties of FG plates are assumed to vary according to a power-law distribution of the volume fraction of the constituents. The equations of motion are derived using the principle of variational energy and virtual work. Analytical solutions are obtained for simply supported plates, and their accuracy is verified by comparing the results with those available in the literature.

2. MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF FG PLATE

In this study, the material properties of an FG plate are considered to vary according to the rule of mixtures [31]. A simple power-law distribution from pure metal on the lower face ($z=-h/2$) to pure ceramic on the upper face ($z=+h/2$) is assumed in terms of the volume fractions of the constituents [32]. The mechanical and physical properties of FGMs are determined from the volume fraction of the material constituents. We assume that material properties such as modulus of elasticity (E), density (ρ) and Poisson's ratio (ν) can be determined by [33-36]:

$$\begin{aligned} E(z) &= E_m + (E_c - E_m) \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^k \\ \rho(z) &= \rho_m + (\rho_c - \rho_m) \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^k \\ \nu(z) &= \nu = \text{const} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where k is the gradient index and subscripts m and c refer to the metal and ceramic constituents, respectively. The value of k equal to zero and infinity represents a fully ceramic and metal plate, respectively.

3. REFINED SHEAR DEFORMATION THEORY

3.1 Kinematics and constitutive equations

Based on the refined shear deformation theory [37], the displacement field can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(x, y, z, t) &= u(x, y, t) - z \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial x} + [f(z)] \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x} \\ u_2(x, y, z, t) &= v(x, y, t) - z \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial y} + [f(z)] \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} \\ u_3(x, y, z, t) &= w_b(x, y, t) + w_s(x, y, t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where u_0 and v_0 are the mid-plane displacements of the plate in the x and y direction, respectively; w_b and w_s are the bending and shear components of transverse displacement, respectively.

Clearly, the displacement field in Eq. (2) contains only four unknowns u_0 , v_0 , w_b and w_s . The nonzero strains associated with the displacement field in Eq. (3) are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} k_x^b \\ k_y^b \\ k_{xy}^b \end{Bmatrix} + f(z) \begin{Bmatrix} k_x^s \\ k_y^s \\ k_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = g(z) \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^s \\ \gamma_{xz}^s \end{Bmatrix} \\
 \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} k_x^b \\ k_y^b \\ k_{xy}^b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial y^2} \\ -2\frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix}, \\
 \begin{Bmatrix} k_x^s \\ k_y^s \\ k_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial y^2} \\ -2\frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial x \partial y} \end{Bmatrix}, \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^s \\ \gamma_{xz}^s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(z) &= z \left[1 + \frac{3\pi}{2} \sec(h)^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{3\pi}{2} h^* \tanh \left(\frac{z}{h} \right) \\
 g(z) &= 1 - f'(z) \\
 f'(z) &= \frac{df(z)}{dz}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

It should be noted that unlike the FSDT, this theory does not require shear correction factors. Moreover, the constitutive relations of a FG plate can be written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{E(z)}{1-\nu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

3.2 Stability equations

The equations of motion are obtained using the principle of variational energy and virtual work [38].

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta u: \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} &= I_0 \ddot{u} - I_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_b}{\partial x} - J_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_s}{\partial x} \\
 \delta v: \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} &= I_0 \ddot{v} - I_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_b}{\partial y} - J_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_s}{\partial y} \\
 \delta w_b: \frac{\partial^2 M_x^b}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}^b}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y^b}{\partial y^2} &= I_0 (\ddot{w}_b + \ddot{w}_s) + I_1 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{u}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \dot{v}}{\partial x} \right) - I_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_b - J_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_s \\
 \delta w_s: \frac{\partial^2 M_x^s}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}^s}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y^s}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial S_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial S_{yz}}{\partial y} &= I_0 (\ddot{w}_b + \ddot{w}_s) + J_1 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{u}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \dot{v}}{\partial x} \right) - J_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_b - K_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_s
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

with

$$(I_0, I_1, J_1, I_2, J_2, K_2) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (1, z, z^2, f(z), zf(z), f^2(z)) \rho(z) dz \tag{7}$$

and

$$\ddot{u} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}; \ddot{v} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2}; \ddot{w}_b = \frac{\partial^2 w_b}{\partial t^2}; \ddot{w}_s = \frac{\partial^2 w_s}{\partial t^2} \tag{8}$$

Using constitutive relations, the stress and moment resultants are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{Bmatrix} N_x & N_y & N_{xy} \\ M_x^b & M_y^b & M_{xy}^b \\ M_x^s & M_y^s & M_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix} &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}) \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ z \\ f(z) \end{Bmatrix} dz \\
 (S_{xz}^s, S_{yz}^s) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}) g(z) dz
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Upon substitution of Eq (3) into Eq. (5) and the subsequent results into Eq. (9) the stress resultants are obtained in the matrix form as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x^b \\ M_y^b \\ M_{xy}^b \\ M_x^s \\ M_y^s \\ M_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & B_{11}^s & B_{12}^s & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & B_{12}^s & B_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & B_{66}^s \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 & D_{11}^s & D_{12}^s & 0 \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 & D_{12}^s & D_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66} & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^s \\ B_{11}^s & B_{12}^s & 0 & D_{11}^s & D_{12}^s & 0 & H_{11}^s & H_{12}^s & 0 \\ B_{12}^s & B_{22}^s & 0 & D_{12}^s & D_{22}^s & 0 & H_{12}^s & H_{22}^s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & B_{66}^s & 0 & 0 & D_{66}^s & 0 & 0 & H_{66}^s \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x^b \\ k_y^b \\ k_{xy}^b \\ k_x^s \\ k_y^s \\ k_{xy}^s \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} S_{yz} \\ S_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44}^s & 0 \\ 0 & A_{55}^s \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where A_{ij} , B_{ij} , D_{ij} , H_{ij} are the plate stiffness, defined by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} & B_{11} & D_{11} & B_{11}^s & D_{11}^s & H_{11}^s \\ A_{12} & B_{12} & D_{12} & B_{12}^s & D_{12}^s & H_{12}^s \\ A_{66} & B_{66} & D_{66} & B_{66}^s & D_{66}^s & H_{66}^s \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{E(z)}{1-\nu^2} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ \nu \\ \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} \end{Bmatrix} dz$$

$$(A_{22}, B_{22}, D_{22}, B_{22}^s, D_{22}^s, H_{22}^s) = (A_{11}, B_{11}, D_{11}, B_{11}^s, D_{11}^s, H_{11}^s)$$

$$A_{44}^s = A_{55}^s = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{E(z)}{2(1+\nu)} [g(z)]^2 dz \quad (11)$$

By substituting Eq. (10) into Eq. (6), the equations of motion can be expressed in terms of displacements (u , v , w_b , w_s) as

$$\begin{aligned} A \left[\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \left(\frac{1-\nu}{2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \left(\frac{1+\nu}{2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} \right] - B \nabla^2 \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial x} - B^s \nabla^2 \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial x} &= I_0 \ddot{u} - I_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_b}{\partial x} - J_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_s}{\partial x} \\ A \left[\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \left(\frac{1-\nu}{2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \left(\frac{1+\nu}{2} \right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} \right] - B \nabla^2 \frac{\partial w_b}{\partial y} - B^s \nabla^2 \frac{\partial w_s}{\partial y} &= I_0 \ddot{v} - I_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_b}{\partial y} - J_1 \frac{\partial \dot{w}_s}{\partial y} \\ B \nabla^2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - D \nabla^4 w_b - D^s \nabla^4 w_s &= I_0 (\ddot{w}_b + \ddot{w}_s) + I_1 \left(\frac{\partial \ddot{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \ddot{v}}{\partial y} \right) - I_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_b - J_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_s \\ B^s \nabla^2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - D^s \nabla^4 w_b - H^s \nabla^4 w_s + A^s \nabla^2 w_s &= I_0 (\ddot{w}_b + \ddot{w}_s) + J_1 \left(\frac{\partial \ddot{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \ddot{v}}{\partial y} \right) - J_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_b - K_2 \nabla^2 \dot{w}_s \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Clearly, when the effect of transverse shear deformation is neglected ($w_s=0$), Eq. (12) yields the equations of motion of FG plate based on the CPT [39].

4. NAVIER SOLUTIONS

The equations of motion admit the Navier solutions for simply supported plates. The variables u , v , w_b , w_s can be written by assuming the following variations

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u(x, y) \\ v(x, y) \\ w_b(x, y) \\ w_s(x, y) \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \begin{Bmatrix} U_{mn} e^{i\omega t} \cos \lambda x \sin \mu y \\ V_{mn} e^{i\omega t} \sin \lambda x \cos \mu y \\ W_{bmn} e^{i\omega t} \sin \lambda x \sin \mu y \\ W_{smn} e^{i\omega t} \sin \lambda x \sin \mu y \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, $\lambda = m\pi/a$, $\mu = n\pi/b$, ω is the natural frequency, and $(U_{mn}, V_{mn}, W_{bmn}, W_{smn})$ are unknown functions. Substituting Eq. (13) into Eq. (12), the following eigenvalue equation is obtained

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} & c_{14} \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} & c_{24} \\ c_{13} & c_{23} & c_{33} & c_{34} \\ c_{14} & c_{24} & c_{34} & c_{44} \end{pmatrix} - \omega^2 \begin{pmatrix} m_{11} & 0 & m_{13} & m_{14} \\ 0 & m_{22} & m_{23} & m_{24} \\ m_{13} & m_{23} & m_{33} & m_{34} \\ m_{14} & m_{24} & m_{34} & m_{44} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_{mn} \\ V_{mn} \\ W_{bmn} \\ W_{smn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_{11} &= A\lambda^2 + \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} A\mu^2; c_{12} = \frac{(1+\nu)}{2} A\lambda\mu; c_{22} = \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} A\lambda^2 + A\mu^2 \\ c_{13} &= -B\lambda(\lambda^2 + \mu^2); c_{14} = -B^s\lambda(\lambda^2 + \mu^2); c_{23} = -B\mu(\lambda^2 + \mu^2) \\ c_{24} &= -B^s\mu(\lambda^2 + \mu^2); c_{33} = D(\lambda^2 + \mu^2)^2; c_{34} = D^s(\lambda^2 + \mu^2)^2 \\ c_{44} &= H^s(\lambda^2 + \mu^2)^2 + A^s(\lambda^2 + \mu^2)^2 \\ m_{11} &= m_{22} = I_0; m_{13} = -\lambda I_1; m_{14} = -\lambda J_1; m_{23} = -\mu I_1; m_{24} = -\mu J_1 \\ m_{33} &= I_0 + I_2(\lambda^2 + \mu^2); m_{34} = I_0 + J_2(\lambda^2 + \mu^2); m_{44} = I_0 + K_2(\lambda^2 + \mu^2) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The natural frequencies of the FG plate can be obtained by setting the determinant of the coefficient matrix in Eq. (14) to zero. For each choice of m and n , there is a corresponding unique value of ω . The fundamental frequency is the smallest value of $\omega(m, n)$.

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, various numerical examples are presented and discussed to verify the accuracy of the present theory in predicting the natural frequency of simply supported plates. Two types of FG plates of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/ZrO₂ are used in this study, in which their material properties are listed in Table 1. For all calculations, the shear correction factor and Poisson's ratio are taken as 5/6 and 0.3, respectively. Comparison results are given for various values of thickness ratio, aspect ratio, and the power law index. For convenience, following natural frequency parameter is used in presenting the numerical results in tabular and graphical forms

$$\bar{\zeta} = \omega h \sqrt{\frac{\rho_m}{E_m}}, \quad \hat{\zeta} = \omega h \sqrt{\frac{\rho_c}{E_c}}, \quad \bar{\omega} = \omega a^2 \frac{\sqrt{\rho_c / E_c}}{h} \quad (16)$$

Table 1: Material properties used in the FG plate

Properties	Metal aluminum (Al)	Ceramic	
		Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	Zirconia (ZrO ₂)
$E(\text{GPa})$	70	380	200
$\rho (\text{kg/m}^3)$	2,702	3,800	5,700

5.1 Comparison studies

The first example is carried out for Al/ZrO₂ square plates with different values of thickness ratio a/h and power law index k . The fundamental frequency parameters are obtained using the preset theory and the CPT. The obtained results are compared with those of 3-D exact solutions of [40], 2-D higher-order theory solutions of [41], HSDT with finite element method solutions of [42], Reddy's theory with analytical method solutions of Hosseini-Hashemi et al. [28], and FSDT with analytical method solutions of Hosseini-Hashemi et al. [8] in Table 2. It can be seen that for the plate with $k=0$, that is, fully ceramic isotropic plate, the results of present theory are well in agreement with those of 3-D, HSDT, and FSDT solutions. However, for FG plate with non-zero values of k , the results of present theory and other shear deformation theories are higher than those obtained by 3-D exact solutions of [40].

The reason for this feature may be due to the way of estimating the material properties of FG plates. In Ref. [40], the material properties at a point were estimated from the local volume fractions using [43] scheme, whereas in the present study and Refs. [8,28,41,42], the material properties are assumed to vary through the thickness of the plate with a power law distribution of the volume fractions of the two materials. The CPT solutions obtained in this study are higher than those predicted by shear deformation theories and 3-D exact solutions. The difference between CPT and shear deformation theories and 3-D exact solutions is more considerable for thick plates. For example, the difference between the CPT and 3-D results, for fully ceramic plate, increases from 2.42 to 18.82% when the a/h ratio is decreased from 10 to $\sqrt{10}$. It can be observed from Table 2 that the results of present theory and [28] are identical. It should be noted that the present theory involves four unknowns as against five unknowns in both FSDT and Reddy's theory.

Table 2: Comparison of fundamental frequency parameter $\bar{\xi}$ of Al/ZrO₂ square plate

Method	$k=0$		$k=5$			$a/h=5$		
	$a/h=10$	$a/h=10$	$a/h=5$	$a/h=10$	$a/h=20$	$k=2$	$k=3$	$k=5$
3-D[40]	0.4658	0.0578	0.2192	0.0596	0.0153	0.2197	0.2211	0.2225
HSDT [41]	0.4658	0.0578	0.2285	0.0619	0.0158	0.2264	0.2270	0.2281
HSDT [42]	0.4658	0.0578	0.2257	0.0613	0.0157	0.2237	0.2243	0.2253
HSDT [28]	0.4623	0.0577	0.2276	0.0619	0.0158	0.2256	0.2263	0.2272
FSDT [8]	0.4618	0.0577	0.2276	0.0169	0.0158	0.2264	0.2276	0.2291
CPT	0.5535	0.0592	0.2479	0.0634	0.0159	0.2473	0.2497	0.2526
Present	0.4623	0.0577	0.2277	0.0619	0.0158	0.2257	0.2263	0.2272

The second example a square Al/Al₂O₃ plate with thickness ratio varied from 5 to 20 and power law index varied from 0 to 10 is analyzed using different plate theories Fundamental frequency and the lowest third frequency parameters are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of natural frequency parameter ξ of Al/Al₂O₃ square plate

a/h	Mode no (m, n)	Method	Power law index k				
			0	0.5	1	4	10
5	(1,1)	HSDT [28]	0.2113	0.1807	0.1631	0.1378	0.1301
		FSDT [8]	0.2112	0.1805	0.1631	0.1397	0.1324
		CPT	0.2314	0.1959	0.1762	0.1524	0.1467
		Present	0.2113	0.1807	0.1631	0.1378	0.1301
	(1,2)	HSDT [28]	0.4623	0.3989	0.3607	0.2980	0.2771
		FSDT [8]	0.4618	0.3978	0.3604	0.3049	0.2856
		CPT	0.5535	0.4681	0.4198	0.3603	0.3481
		Present	0.4623	0.3989	0.3607	0.2980	0.2771
	(2,2)	HSDT [28]	0.6688	0.5803	0.5254	0.4284	0.3948
		FSDT [8]	0.6676	0.5779	0.5245	0.4405	0.4097
		CPT	0.8504	0.7184	0.6425	0.5478	0.5306
		Present	0.6688	0.5803	0.5254	0.4284	0.3948
0	(1,1)	HSDT [28]	0.0577	0.0490	0.0442	0.0381	0.0364
		FSDT [8]	0.0577	0.0490	0.0442	0.0382	0.0366
		CPT	0.0592	0.0502	0.0452	0.0392	0.0377
		Present	0.0577	0.0490	0.0442	0.0381	0.0364
	(1,2)	HSDT [28]	0.1377	0.1174	0.1059	0.0903	0.0856
		FSDT [8]	0.1376	0.1173	0.1059	0.0911	0.0867
		CPT	0.1464	0.1239	0.1115	0.0966	0.0930
		Present	0.1377	0.1174	0.1059	0.0903	0.0856
	(2,2)	HSDT [28]	0.2113	0.1807	0.1631	0.1378	0.1301
		FSDT [8]	0.2112	0.1805	0.1631	0.1397	0.1324
		CPT	0.2314	0.1959	0.1762	0.1524	0.1467
		Present	0.2113	0.1807	0.1631	0.1378	0.1301
20	(1,1)	HSDT [28]	0.0148	0.0125	0.0113	0.0098	0.0094
		FSDT [8]	0.0148	0.0125	0.0113	0.0098	0.0094
		CPT	0.0149	0.0126	0.0114	0.0099	0.0095
		Present	0.0148	0.0125	0.0113	0.0098	0.0094

It can be seen that the results obtained by present theory are in good agreement with those reported by [28] based on Reddy's theory, and [8] based on FSDT. The results also indicate that the CPT overpredicts the natural frequency of FG plates, especially for the thick plate at higher modes of vibration. For example, the differences in values predicted by the CPT and present theory, for fully ceramic thick plate with $a/h=5$, are 9.51, 19.28 and 27.5% corresponding to the first, second and third modes of vibration, respectively. Such behavior is due to the influence of rotary inertia and transverse shear deformation in thick plate. Therefore, in order to obtain accurate natural frequencies for thick plates, it is necessary to consider the rotary inertia and transverse shear deformation effects by using shear deformation theories.

The last example is performed for rectangular Al/Al₂O₃ plate ($b=2a$) with thickness ratio varied from 5 to 20 and power law index varied from 0 to 10. The lowest four frequency parameters obtained from present theory and Reddy's theory are compared with those reported by [8] based on FSDT in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of frequency parameter $\bar{\omega}$ of Al/Al₂O₃ rectangular plate ($b=2a$)

a/h	Mode no (m, n)	Method	Power law index k						
			0	0.5	1	2	5	8	10
5	1(1,1)	FSDT [8]	3.4409	2.9322	2.6473	2.4017	2.2528	2.1985	2.1677
		HSDT	3.4412	2.9347	2.6475	2.3949	2.2272	2.1697	2.1407
		Present	3.4412	2.9347	2.6475	2.3949	2.2272	2.1697	2.1407
	2(1,2)	FSDT [8]	5.2802	4.5122	4.0773	3.6953	3.4492	3.3587	3.3094
		HSDT	5.2813	4.5180	4.0781	3.6805	3.3938	3.2964	3.2514
		Present	5.2813	4.5180	4.0781	3.6805	3.3938	3.2964	3.2514
	3(1,3)	FSDT [8]	8.0710	6.9231	6.2636	5.6695	5.2579	5.045	5.0253
		HSDT	8.0749	6.9366	6.2663	5.6390	5.1425	4.9758	4.9055
		Present	8.0749	6.9366	6.2663	5.6390	5.1425	4.9758	4.9055
4 (2,1)	FSDT [8]	9.7416	8.6926	7.8711	7.1189	6.5749	5.9062	5.7518	
	HSDT	10.1164	8.7138	7.8762	7.0751	6.4074	6.1846	6.0954	
	Present	0.1164	8.7138	7.8762	7.0751	6.4074	6.1846	6.0954	
10	1(1,1)	FSDT [8]	3.6518	3.0983	2.7937	2.5386	2.3998	2.3504	2.3197
		HSDT	3.6518	3.0990	2.7937	2.5364	2.3916	2.3411	2.3110
		Present	3.6518	3.0990	2.7937	2.5364	2.3916	2.3411	2.3110
	2 (1,2)	FSDT [8]	5.7693	4.8997	4.4192	4.0142	3.7881	3.7072	3.6580
		HSDT	5.7694	4.9014	4.4192	4.0090	3.7682	3.6846	3.6368
		Present	5.7694	4.9014	4.4192	4.0090	3.7682	3.6846	3.6368
	3 (1,3)	FSDT [8]	9.1876	7.8145	7.0512	6.4015	6.0247	5.8887	5.8086
		HSDT	9.1880	7.8189	7.0515	6.3886	5.9765	5.8341	5.7575
		Present	9.1880	7.8189	7.0515	6.3886	5.9765	5.8341	5.7575
	4 (2,1)	FSDT [8]	11.8310	10.0740	9.0928	8.2515	7.7505	7.5688	7.4639
		HSDT	11.8315	10.0810	9.0933	8.2309	7.6731	7.4813	7.3821
		Present	11.8315	10.0810	9.0933	8.2309	7.6731	7.4813	7.3821
20	1(1,1)	FSDT [8]	3.7123	3.1456	2.8352	2.5777	2.4425	2.3948	2.3642
		HSDT	3.7123	3.1458	2.8352	2.5771	2.4403	2.3923	2.3619
		Present	3.7123	3.1458	2.8352	2.5771	2.4403	2.3923	2.3619
	2 (1,2)	FSDT [8]	5.9198	5.0175	4.5228	4.1115	3.8939	3.8170	3.7681
		HSDT	5.9199	5.0180	4.5228	4.1100	3.8884	3.8107	3.7622
		Present	5.9199	5.0180	4.5228	4.1100	3.8884	3.8107	3.7622
	3 (1,3)	FSDT [8]	9.5668	8.1121	7.3132	6.6471	6.2903	6.1639	6.0843
		HSDT	9.5669	8.1133	7.3132	6.6433	6.2760	6.1476	6.0690
		Present	9.5669	8.1133	7.3132	6.6433	6.2760	6.1476	6.0690
	4 (2,1)	FSDT [8]	12.4560	10.5660	9.5261	8.6572	8.1875	8.0207	7.9166
		HSDT	12.4562	10.5677	9.5261	8.6509	8.1636	7.9934	7.8909
		Present	12.4562	10.5677	9.5261	8.6509	8.1636	7.9934	7.8909

Again, the present theory and Reddy's theory give identical results. Meanwhile, the FSDT [8] gives accurate results for moderately thick plate at lower modes of vibration. For higher

modes of vibration, however, there is slight difference between the results of FSDT and Reddy's theory. The maximum difference between the FSDT and HSDT is 5.64% at the fourth mode of thick plate ($a/h=5$, $k=10$).

5.2 Parameter studies

After verifying the accuracy and efficiency of the present solution, parameter studies are carried out to investigate the effects of variations of power law index, thickness ratio, and aspect ratio on natural frequency of FGM plates. The natural frequency parameters of Al/Al₂O₃ plates are obtained using the CPT, HSDT of Reddy, and present theory.

Figure 1 illustrates the variation of fundamental frequency parameters of square plate versus power law index. The thickness ratios a/h are assumed to be 5 (corresponding to thick plate) and 100 (corresponding to thin plate). It can be seen that the fundamental frequency parameter decreases as the power law index increases. This is due to the fact that increasing the power law index increases the volume fraction of metal. Also, the frequency parameters of fully ceramic plates are considerably higher than those of FG plates. Furthermore, the results predicted by the present theory and HSDT are identical, and the CPT overestimates frequency parameter of FG plates. The difference between CPT and present theory is considerable for thick plate, but it can be neglected for thin plates.

Fig 1: The effect of power of FGM on fundamental frequency parameter of square plate (Al/Al₂O₃)

The variation of fundamental frequency parameter of square plate versus thickness ratio a/h is shown in Fig. 2. It is observed that the fundamental frequency parameter increases by the increase in thickness ratio, and the variation of fundamental frequency parameter

is remarkable when the thickness ratio is smaller than 5. Also, the CPT overestimates the frequency parameter of FG plates, and the discrepancy between the CPT and present curves is negligible when the thickness ratio is greater than 10.

Fig 2: The effect of thickness ratio on fundamental frequency parameter of square plate (Al/Al₂O₃)

The effect of aspect ratio b/a on the frequency parameter of plate ($a/h=10$) is presented in Fig. 3. It can be found that the frequency parameter decreases by the increase in the aspect ratio.

Fig 3: The effect of aspect ratio on fundamental frequency parameter of rectangular plate ($a=10h$, Al/Al₂O₃)

The first nine frequency parameters $\bar{\omega}$ have been tabulated in Tables 5 and 6 for square and rectangular plates, respectively.

Table 5: First nine frequency parameter $\bar{\omega}$ of Al/Al₂O₃ square plate

<i>a/h</i>	Mode no (<i>m,n</i>)	Power law index <i>k</i>						
		0	0.5	1	2	5	10	100
5	1(1,1)	5.2813	4.5180	4.0781	3.6805	3.3938	3.2514	2.8204
	2(2,1)	11.5563	9.9716	9.0166	8.0905	7.2944	6.9270	6.1369
	3(1,2)	11.5563	9.9716	9.0166	8.0905	7.2944	6.9270	6.1369
	4(2,2)	16.7207	14.5064	13.1354	11.7487	10.4507	9.8703	8.8508
	5(3,1)	19.7648	17.1939	15.5813	13.9166	12.2984	11.5840	10.4464
	6(1,3)	19.7648	17.1939	15.5813	13.9166	12.2984	11.5840	10.4464
	7(3,2)	23.9024	20.8603	8.9239	16.8765	14.8013	13.8967	12.6124
	8(2,3)	23.9024	20.8603	8.9239	16.8765	14.8013	13.8967	12.6124
	9(4,1)	28.8270	25.2402	22.925	20.4180	17.7735	16.6330	15.878
10	1(1,1)	5.7694	4.9014	4.4192	4.0090	3.7682	3.6368	3.0962
	2(2,1)	13.7650	11.7387	10.5901	9.5795	8.9087	8.5628	7.3669
	3(1,2)	13.7650	11.7387	10.5901	9.5795	8.9087	8.5628	7.3669
	4(2,2)	21.1253	18.0719	16.3124	14.7221	13.5752	13.0054	11.2817
	5(3,1)	25.7417	22.0607	19.9195	17.9547	16.4765	15.7556	13.7303
	6(1,3)	25.7417	22.0607	19.9195	17.9547	16.4765	15.7556	13.7303
	7(3,2)	32.2995	27.7465	25.0650	22.5558	20.5699	19.6221	17.2011
	8(2,3)	32.2995	27.7465	25.0650	22.5558	20.5699	19.6221	17.2011
	9(4,1)	40.4655	34.8553	3.5047	28.3003	25.6295	24.3817	21.5126
20	1(1,1)	5.9199	5.0180	4.5228	4.1100	3.8884	3.7622	3.1821
	2(2,1)	14.6071	12.3961	11.1747	10.1458	9.5664	9.2440	7.8452
	3(1,2)	14.6071	12.3961	11.1747	10.1458	9.5664	9.2440	7.8452
	4(2,2)	23.0777	9.6058	17.6769	16.0358	15.0729	14.5474	12.3847
	5(3,1)	28.6115	24.3239	21.9332	19.8864	18.6555	17.9914	15.3467
	6(1,3)	28.6115	24.3239	21.9332	19.8864	18.6555	17.9914	15.3467
	7(3,2)	36.7522	3.2757	28.2060	25.5546	23.9059	23.0300	19.6991
	8(2,3)	36.7522	3.2757	28.2060	25.5546	23.9059	23.0300	19.6991
	9(4,1)	47.3260	40.3240	36.3733	32.9234	30.6926	29.5285	25.3443
100	1(1,1)	5.9712	5.0575	4.5579	4.1445	3.9299	3.8058	3.2116
	2(2,1)	14.9198	12.6375	11.3892	10.3558	9.8182	9.5076	8.0243
	3(1,2)	14.9198	12.6375	11.3892	10.3558	9.8182	9.5076	8.0243
	4(2,2)	23.8587	20.2099	18.2139	16.5605	15.6986	15.2010	12.8314
	5(3,1)	29.8126	25.2541	22.7600	20.6934	19.6145	18.9921	16.0331
	6(1,3)	29.8126	25.2541	22.7600	20.6934	19.6145	18.9921	16.0331
	7(3,2)	38.7353	32.8141	29.5736	26.8873	25.4817	24.6718	20.8309
	8(2,3)	38.7353	32.8141	29.5736	26.8873	25.4817	24.6718	20.8309
	9(4,1)	50.6172	42.8826	38.6481	35.1357	33.2926	32.2319	27.2194

Table 6: First nine frequency parameter $\bar{\omega}$ of Al/Al₂O₃ rectangular plate ($a=1.5b$)

a/h	Mode no (m, n)	Power law index k						
		0	0.5	1	2	5	10	100
5	1(1,1)	8.0749	6.9366	6.2663	5.6390	5.1425	4.9055	4.3003
	2(2,1)	13.8117	11.9477	10.8101	9.6850	8.6769	8.2191	7.3234
	3(1,2)	19.7648	17.1939	15.5813	13.9166	12.2984	11.5840	10.4464
	4(3,1)	12.5440	18.7687	17.0163	15.1875	13.3756	12.5805	11.3781
	5(2,2)	23.9024	20.8603	18.9239	16.8765	14.8013	13.8967	12.6124
	6(3,2)	29.9748	26.2631	23.8607	21.2462	18.4659	17.2690	15.7879
	7(4,1)	30.2572	26.5149	24.0911	21.4502	18.6362	17.4255	15.9355
	8(1,3)	33.5185	29.4251	26.7560	23.8095	20.6036	19.2305	17.6405
	9(2,3)	36.5740	32.1558	29.2594	26.0268	22.4479	20.9200	19.2381
10	1(1,1)	9.1880	7.8189	7.0515	6.3886	5.9765	5.7575	4.9248
	2(2,1)	16.9009	14.4328	13.0236	11.7688	10.9037	10.4651	9.0366
	3(1,2)	25.7417	22.0607	19.9195	17.9547	16.4765	15.7556	13.7303
	4(3,1)	28.5242	24.4705	22.0998	19.9056	18.2171	17.4015	15.2040
	5(2,2)	32.2995	27.7465	25.0650	22.5558	20.5699	19.6221	17.2011
	6(3,2)	42.4174	36.5587	33.0488	29.6759	26.8336	25.5116	22.5416
	7(4,1)	42.9002	36.9803	33.4311	30.0163	27.1312	25.7906	22.7961
	8(1,3)	48.5442	41.9154	37.9072	33.9996	30.6021	29.0412	25.7685
	9(2,3)	53.9350	46.6398	42.1953	37.8114	33.9055	32.1277	28.6040
20	1(1,1)	9.5669	8.1133	7.3132	6.6433	6.2760	6.0690	5.1407
	2(2,1)	18.1620	15.4200	13.9016	12.6171	11.8808	11.4745	9.7511
	3(1,2)	28.6115	24.3239	21.9332	19.8864	18.6555	17.9914	15.3467
	4(3,1)	32.0262	27.2384	24.5627	22.2635	20.8607	20.1088	17.1731
	5(2,2)	36.7522	31.2757	28.2060	25.5546	23.9059	23.0300	19.6991
	6(3,2)	49.9221	42.5486	38.3818	34.7338	32.3535	31.1166	26.7289
	7(4,1)	50.5682	43.1025	38.8819	35.844	32.7666	31.5114	27.0735
	8(1,3)	58.2353	49.6803	44.8220	40.5338	37.6589	36.1832	31.1595
	9(2,3)	65.7484	56.1357	50.6530	45.7794	42.4370	40.7388	35.1593
100	1(1,1)	9.7010	8.2167	7.4051	6.7333	6.3844	6.1826	5.2176
	2(2,1)	18.6455	15.7936	14.2336	12.9419	12.2693	11.8809	10.0279
	3(1,2)	29.8126	25.254	22.7600	20.6934	19.6145	18.9921	16.0331
	4(3,1)	33.5316	28.4050	25.5998	23.2750	22.0601	21.3596	18.0328
	5(2,2)	38.7353	32.8141	29.5736	26.8873	25.4817	24.6718	20.8309
	6(3,2)	53.5850	45.3976	40.9148	37.1960	35.2431	34.1197	28.8150
	7(4,1)	54.3268	46.0262	41.4814	37.7110	35.7306	34.5915	29.2138
	8(1,3)	63.2230	53.5658	48.2769	43.8871	4.5764	40.2486	33.9964
	9(2,3)	72.1097	61.0981	55.0658	50.0567	47.4144	45.8976	38.7735

The FG plates are made of Al/Al₂O₃. In each table, four different values of thickness ratio 5, 10 (corresponding to moderately thick plate) and 20, 100 (corresponding to thin plate) are examined. In addition, seven arbitrary values of power law index ($p= 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10$ and 100) are considered. Following points can be noticeable from Tables 5 and 6:

- i. Regardless of mode number and power law index, frequency parameter increases by increasing thickness ratio. The effect of thickness ratio becomes more significant for

higher mode of natural frequencies. Such behavior is due to the influence of rotary inertia and shear deformations.

- ii. Regardless of mode number and thickness ratio, frequency parameter increases by decreasing power law index.

The effect of side-to-thickness ratio (a/h), aspect ratio (a/b) and modulus ratio (E_m/E_c) on fundamental frequencies for a square Al/ZrO₂ FG plate are illustrated in Figures 4, 5 and 6.

Fig. 4: The effect of thickness ratio for various power law index on fundamental frequency parameter of square plate (Al/ZrO₂)

Fig. 5: The effect of aspect ratio for various power law index on fundamental frequency parameter of rectangular plate ($a=5h$, Al/ZrO₂)

Fig. 6: The effect of modulus ratio for various power law index on fundamental frequency parameter of rectangular plate ($a=5h$, Al/ZrO₂)

6. CONCLUSION

A refined and simple higher-order shear deformation theory using a new hyperbolic warping function is developed and implemented in the present work for free vibration analysis of functionally graded (FG) plates [44]. The accuracy of this theory has been demonstrated through the vibration analysis of simply supported FG plates. The conclusions of this theory are as follows:

- i. The natural frequencies predicted by this theory are identical to those obtained by Reddy's theory, which is the most widely used for FG plates [45].
- ii. This theory involves only four unknowns, compared to the five unknowns in Reddy's theory and the First-Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT).
- iii. This theory does not require a shear correction factor, unlike the FSDT.
- iv. It shares strong similarities with the Classical Plate Theory (CPT) in many aspects, such as equations of motion, boundary conditions, and stress resultant expressions [46].

In conclusion, it can be said that this theory is not only accurate but also efficient in predicting the natural frequency of FG plates.

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